

e

Full Proposal

**Sustainable software
2023 (SS 2023)**

e

REGISTRATION FORM (BASIC DATA)

This document contains explanatory text in italics. Please remove this text before submission.

1a. Lead Applicant (LA). The Lead Applicant (LA) is the contact person for all correspondence.

Surname, first name, title(s)	
Position	
Institute	
Department	
Section	
Address	
Postal code	
City	
Telephone	
E-mail	
Name of eScience Center co-author	
E-mail of eScience Center co-author	

2a. Title of the project and acronym

A short and specific title for the proposed research. Please also use a project acronym as part of the title.

2b. Summary for the eScience Center website (max. 150 words)

Please provide a non-expert summary of the proposal for use on the eScience Center website and other media. This summary will be made public only in case the proposal is awarded. The eScience Center reserves the right to edit the text for reasons of consistency, correctness, formatting, or otherwise.

2c. Abstract of the work to be performed (max. 250 words)

Please provide an expert research abstract of the work to be performed for the benefit of the reviewers.

2d. Keywords

(max. 6 keywords)

2e. Link with eScience Center expertise

Indicate the area of expertise the proposed work is expected to require. Select as many as necessary.

- Software quality** (developing workflow technologies, improving software practices, advancing software sustainability)
- AI** (machine learning, image processing)
- Analytics** (big data analytics, text analysis, visualization)
- Data processing** (databases, real-time data analysis, interoperability and linked data)
- Computing** (exploitation of hardware accelerators, high performance computing, cloud computing, combining simulations)

2f. Project duration

Indicative project start date:

Indicative project end date:

Requested PYR:

In-kind funding will be provided in the form of one or more Research Software Engineers (RSEs) employed by the eScience Center. The eScience Center will allocate sufficient RSEs to carry out the research proposal, depending on the project requirements and the requested eScience expertise.

The project duration should be between 18 and 24 months. A project may be requested for an in-kind budget of 2.0 PYR. A project should start at the latest 12 months after the granting decision.

Note that the above project start and end dates are indicative only. The exact dates will be determined by the eScience Center in close consultation with the LA and the Research Team.

2g. Research Team

Name	Affiliation	Position	Contribution (FTE)	Expertise & type of involvement
<i>Lead Applicant</i>			<i>at least 0.1 required</i>	
<i>Co-applicant / Team member</i>			<i>no requirement</i>	

<i>Co-applicant / Team member</i>			<i>no requirement</i>	
<i>eScience Center RSE (unnamed)</i>	<i>eScience Center</i>	<i>RSE</i>	<i>requested</i>	
<i>eScience Center RSE (unnamed)</i>	<i>eScience Center</i>	<i>RSE</i>	<i>requested</i>	
<i>Add/remove as many rows as required</i>				

The proposal should be submitted in collaboration with a senior member of the Netherlands eScience Center acting as co-author.

The LA should either come from a domain-oriented research discipline with a focus on technology development, or from a technical discipline (e.g., data science, computer science, AI). The LA must be in possession of a PhD.

The LA should demonstrate knowledge and experience in developing digital methodologies. This should be reflected in Section 3a and in the list of key publications in Section 3e.

The Research Team consists of at least the LA and one or more RSEs employed by the eScience Center. The Research Team can include researchers from research performing organizations other than that of the LA. The Research Team should make clear its availability for a collaborative effort.

Public-private collaborations are possible, but the inclusion of industrial partners in the Research Team is not required.

Note that the requested RSEs will be allocated by the eScience Center. It cannot be guaranteed at the time of proposal submission, or at the time of project awarding, that any specific RSEs will be allocated to the project. For this reason, it suffices to include unnamed eScience Center RSEs.

PROJECT PROPOSAL

3. Project proposal

The text and illustrations should facilitate easy reading and should be self-contained. References are allowed and will not count towards the word limits. In case there is overlap with the software management plan, refer to that plan for details.

3a. Technological quality and state-of-the-art (max. 1000 words)

- *the proposal must indicate the technological and/or methodological challenges that need to be overcome;*
- *the proposal should discuss relevant existing technologies and methodologies;*
- *the proposal must indicate how the proposed work is connected with efforts within the broader research community;*
- *the research team including the LA should make clear its availability for, and track record concerning, a collaborative effort, and argue why this is sufficient on the basis of a realistic project structure outline.*

3b. Impact (max. 800 words)

- *the proposal must indicate which outcomes the projected software solution(s) are expected to lead to;*
- *the proposed research should potentially change the modus operandi in one or more research disciplines, in terms of broadness, scale, speed of result delivery, or otherwise;*
- *the proposal must indicate which efforts are made to promote the results of the project, in terms both of academic publication and of research community (demonstrations, posters, presentations, workshops, training, etc.).*

3c. Re-use and sustainability (max. 800 words)

- *the proposal must indicate how the technology and software will find use beyond the proposed work itself, preferably across institutional, national or disciplinary borders, both during and after finalization of the project;*
- *the technological and software deliverables must be open source/open access and permit use and/or interpretation by other researchers;*
- *the proposal must indicate how the project will build further collaborations, in academic research, industry, or both;*
- *the proposal must indicate how long-term maintenance and sustainability of project results (in particular software and data) will be secured and managed.*

3d. Software and data accessibility and quality (Health Check)

The eScience Center expects a basic level of accessibility and quality for the data and software used in the projects. Applicants must therefore provide convincing arguments that the data (if any) and software serving as starting points of the research are usable, and do not require substantial cleaning or overhaul. For research software and data that are crucial to the research, the proposal must include the following information:

On data (if applicable):

- *A location where the data can be accessed (preferably a URL).*
- *The license under which the data is distributed (if any).*
- *Special conditions limiting the use of the data (e.g. AVG/GDPR).*

On software (always):

- *A location where the software can be accessed (preferably a URL to a version control system).*
- *The license under which the software is distributed (if any).*
- *A location where the documentation can be accessed (preferably a URL).*

If the data or software are not available online as open data or open source, details must be provided, such as clear metadata, such that an accessibility and quality check can be performed. Please contact the eScience Center to discuss alternatives.

Your institute may employ data stewards who can advise on these topics. Additionally, information on software and data quality can be found at:

- <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-openly-license-research-data>
- <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>
- <https://choosealicense.com>
- <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>

3e. Key publications

Please list a number of (max 5) key publications by the Lead Applicant and/or members of the Research Team relevant to the proposal.

Note that the list of key publications must demonstrate the LA's knowledge and experience in developing digital methodologies.

4. Project structure outline and deliverables (max. 800 words)

Please provide a realistic project structure outline and argue why this is sufficient and appropriate to reach the project outcomes. In particular, the foreseen activities of the LA and of the eScience Center RSEs should be integral to the project structure outline. Focus on "what" must be done, not on "how" this must be done.

Note that the project structure outline will serve as a basis for the detailed project work plan that is established at the start of the project together with the eScience Center. The work plan developed in this manner will define the activities of the eScience Center RSEs, as well as the projected timelines.

Deliverables can include: academic publications, demonstrations, posters, presentations, software, datasets, documentation, and tutorials.

5. Workshop plans (max. 150 words)

The organization of one substantial workshop is mandatory. The goal of these workshops may include technology development, as well as community engagement. Workshop proposals are NOT part of the full proposal; these are to be written after the project is awarded. Successful LAs should negotiate the format and costs of the workshops with the eScience Center.

Please describe the topic(s) for the foreseen workshop(s), indicate in what way the technological and software developments of the proposed research project are integrated in the workshop(s), and describe how the workshop(s) will establish lasting connections with relevant communities (academic, industrial, or otherwise).

6. Requirements regarding digital infrastructure (max. 200 words in total for 6a-6d)

Applicants are asked to indicate the project's infrastructural needs (if any) and explain how they expect to fulfil those needs. In most cases, a rough estimate (order of magnitude) is sufficient. In case of doubt, please contact the eScience Center.

In all cases a brief explanation of the choice for specific infrastructures is required. Valid options include, but are not limited to, the following:

- *The Dutch national infrastructure, including facilities offered by SURF (www.surf.nl/en/research-ict) and DANS (<https://dans.knaw.nl>). For more information, it is advisable to contact the organizations responsible for these resources directly.*
- *Proposals may suggest the use of local, international and/or commercial (e.g. web, cloud, etc) hardware and services.*

6a. Compute services

This includes compute hours on CPU clusters, high performance computing (MPI, OpenMP) and the use of accelerators (GPUs, FPGAs).

6b. Data storage & management

Specific requirements for storage. For example, temporary disk storage and/or archival tape storage.

6c. Data transfers

Specific requirements regarding (high-speed) networks.

6d. Other requirements

Specific components (such as software, data sets or specialized hardware) necessary for the proposed research.

ADMINISTRATIVE DETAILS

7. Statements by the applicant

The eScience Center strictly applies the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the EU regulation aimed at strengthening data protection for all individuals within the EU. In the Netherlands the regulation is implemented as the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG)'. Applicants must strictly apply these rules and regulations, as well as the principles, in as much as these are applicable to the proposed work.

The eScience Center endorses the Code Openness Animal Experiments and the Biosecurity Code of Conduct (available at www.knaw.nl). Applicants must check whether the codes have relevance to their application. If so, the eScience Center requires applicants to endorse the code(s) and act according to these. In case of the Biosecurity Code the applicant is convinced that the knowledge presented in the application cannot lead to dual use.

Applicants are asked to endorse and follow the Netherlands eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and Intellectual Property (available at www.esciencecenter.nl). For alternative IP agreements, contact the eScience Center before proposal submission.

- I endorse and follow the rules and regulations as laid out in the Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG), as well as the underlying principles (GDPR).
- I endorse and follow the Code Openness Animal Experiments (if applicable).
- I endorse and follow the eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and IP. **If not ticked, please justify, and contact the eScience Center before submitting the proposal.**
- I have informed my employing institute of the submission of this proposal, by sending a copy of the application to the formally mandated representative of my research organization (e.g. director, head of department, dean).
- I have completed this form truthfully.

Name (Lead Applicant):

Location:

Date:

ATTACHED DOCUMENTS

For the submission of the full proposal the following additional document is required:

- A Software Management Plan (see Section 2.4 of the Call for Proposals).

Optional letters of support or intent can also be attached (see section 2.6 of the Call for Proposals).